

YOUTH POLICY AND THE PLACE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TURKMENISTAN

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Under the leadership of our Esteemed President, great work is being carried out in our independent, permanently neutral state of Turkmenistan during the revival of a new era of a powerful state. The adoption of the Law of Turkmenistan “On state policy towards youth” in the “Year of the Epoch of the people with Arkadag” and the decision of the Mejlis of Turkmenistan to declare 2023 the “Year of youth with Arkadagly Serdar” are clear evidence of the concern for young people in the country at the state level. This law is of great historical and social significance. In our country, ample opportunities and conditions have been created for young people to be able to get an education and master a profession.

The adoption of the Law of Turkmenistan “On state policy towards youth” in order to introduce the best international and world experience in the field of youth policy in the country also paved the way for the implementation of large-scale measures to develop cooperation with foreign countries, as well as with the United Nations Permanent Coordinating Bureau in Turkmenistan, the United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF), the United Nations Development Program and the United Nations Population Fund. Our independent, permanently neutral state of Turkmenistan is expanding multifaceted relations and developing cooperation with many countries of the world. The domestic and foreign policy of our country is adopted by the countries of the world at an exemplary level. We can proudly note that young people make a worthy contribution to the comprehensive development of our country.

Domestic and foreign policy of our country is adopted by world countries at a standard level. Our Esteemed President Serdar Berdimuhamedov said: “With our initiative, the following resolutions were adopted at the 76th session of the General Assembly “Integrating public cycling for sustainable development”, “Central Asia is a zone of peace, trust and cooperation”, and at the 77th session, “Year 2023 as an international year of dialogue as a guarantee of peace”. The awarding of an international certificate to the city of Ashgabat for its contribution to the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe’s “Gardens in the City” initiative is a recognition of the country’s achievements in environmental and environmental protection”, marking it as a recognition of the high reputation of the Motherland at the international level. It is a matter of pride to note that the youth have a worthy contribution in the all-round development of our country. The active participation of youth and students in the bicycle rally on June 3 – the World Bicycle Day is a testimony of the indomitable enthusiasm of youth for the sake of the development of the Motherland. Students also actively participate in the annual autumn and spring gardening events in the country. This shows that the state of Turkmenistan pays great attention to the issue of protecting nature, preserving and increasing its resources, introducing “green” technologies into the economy. It should be noted that the Law of Turkmenistan “On State youth policy” has an important role for the active participation of young people in these issues of international importance, for them to show their abilities in this field.

It is noted in **paragraph 8** of the National program of social and economic development of Turkmenistan in 2022-2052 **entitled “Main directions of industrial and innovative development of economic sectors”**: “The development strategy of Turkmenistan for the future period is to introduce new innovative technologies, including digital technologies and leading international practices in various sectors of the national economy, to move to electronic document circulation and electronic identity card system, to create an innovative, high-tech, competitive digital economy and a well-functioning electronic industry”. Young people also have a rightful place in the work to be done to develop the national innovation system of the country, to establish innovative works, and to introduce new innovative technologies into production. Giving a great place to innovative technologies in the future development of the country requires the training of qualified young people in this field. Formation of a generation of specialists and scientists who can use innovative technologies in higher educational institutions of our country is of great importance for the successful implementation of the tasks ahead in this field.

Under the wise leadership of the President of Turkmenistan, successfully implemented in the “Program of social and economic development of the country of the President of Turkmenistan in 2019-2025”, “Concept of development of digital economy in Turkmenistan in 2019-2025”, as well as in the “State program for the development of the digital economy in Turkmenistan for 2021-2025”, the main principles of the development of the digital economy for the medium and long-term future in the country by diversifying our national economy, increasing its competitiveness and continuously moving towards the industrial-innovation direction of development, and methods are defined. In this field, the work of young people is also important.